

TRANSLATION OF THE IMAGERY OF NATURE IN THE NOVEL
“DAYS GONE BY” BY ABDULLA QADIRI

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Abstract: This current study aims to investigate translated version of “Days gone by” (Utkan kunlar) by Abdulla Kodiri. The main purpose of the research is to study the image of nature expressed in the novel on the basis of nationality in translation and to express similarities and differences between the translation versions.

Keywords: The days gone by, nationality, image of nature, similarity, difference.

INTRODUCTON

All of us have encountered the depiction of natural scenes in works of art, of course. This shows how rich the artist's skills are. Because in the depiction of natural scenes, the attitude of the creator to the place he is painting, how well he knows the place, how deeply he feels the world of the characters and the environment in which they live is known. That's why the depiction of natural scenes in works of art is considered the main component of the work¹ In the work of art, the author uses pictorial and expressive means to realize his goal.

The natural scenes in the work allow the reader to imagine something, feel a certain feeling, see, hear, and create images in the human mind. , figurative features, ways of expressing events in different ways are expressive means. Reviving the image of nature in literary translation and the problem of choosing words requires great skill from the author. "The translator - in order to recreate the work in another language, i.e. the native language, matures the author's thoughts, absorbs them, then chooses an alternative word depending on the character of the text, the meaning, resonance, form,

¹1 Aminova L. The issues of artistic skill in the works of the Turkish writer Yashar Kamal, a dissertation written for the degree of Philology, T.: 2003

and stylistic alternative of these words , is concerned with expressing the original idea as fully as possible"² - writes GaybullaSalomov.

It should be noted that the features of the author's skill are determined through the artistic image and means of expression used in the creation of the work. One such tool is the depiction of nature in a work of art. The uniqueness of nature is certainly reflected in man and his psyche. From birth to death, a person lives in harmony with nature and enjoys its beauty. Being inspired by nature is characteristic not only of mankind, but of all creatures of the world. All people can create their own impressions from the beauties of nature, but only artists, including writers and poets, can express these impressions in works using artistic words and paints.

DISCUSSION AND RESULTS

No matter which work we read, we will certainly encounter the image of nature. A real artist depicts man in constant harmony with mother nature. Each artist, while creating a work of art, looks at each event, natural scene, reality in general with his own eyes. Based on the general idea of the work, he chooses a suitable detail and through that selected detail expresses the idea that has a significant place in the content of the work. For example, the image of "spring", which is often found in works of art, is interpreted differently by everyone: "a clean and pleasant spring", "a season of beauty and rejuvenation", "spring freshness" and so on. similar natural phenomena represent the positive aspects of the human psyche, the beauty of life, the content of the refreshing freshness, while images such as "cold raindrops", "black cloud" represent negative situations in the human psyche, fear, inner turmoil , indicates danger or depression. In such images, the writer submits the spring season, which is a part of nature, to the will of the work, expresses the inner experiences of the heroes of the work, their attitude to reality through this image, and the unique style of the creator is revealed. If the translator does not clarify these aspects before translating the work, the author's content cannot be conveyed to the readers in the translation. As a result, the

²G. Salomov, *The Art of Translation*, Tashkent, 1973, p. 57.

author's style may be damaged in the translation.³

When Abdulla Qadiri uses the image of nature, he often uses animations, similes, and adjectives. For example, an excerpt from the chapter of the novel entitled "A Deadly Message and a Scary Night" ("Jonsiz bir xabar va qo'rqinch bir kech")⁴

"Although it was the fifteenth of the month, the moon was invisible with the clouds of the sky, it was a dark night of dark autumn. The clutter of Khoja Maoz's tomb, which had been in existence for hundreds of years, was like a source of darkness. The force was running in all directions, as if a wind was blowing, as if preparing for something. A madman with long hair and a beard was sitting in a corner of the tomb, trying to light a fire as if he were fighting against this terrible darkness. The campfire was swaying from side to side with a bowl in his hand. The wind grew stronger and stronger, the bushes became chaotic, one and a half of the fallen leaves rustled, and the crows and ravens became restless during the same sleep. They began to roll over the bush with a roar. The wind grew stronger and stronger, and the tomb became even more terrifying. The wind blew one after another, and the branches that could not stand it cracked, and the old trees shrieked. They cried out in supplication. The wind was overflowing with rage, squealing as if trying to crush what was standing on the ground..."⁵

Let's compare the translation of this passage with the original one :

"Oyning o'n beshlari bo'lsa-da, havoning bulutlig'i bilanoy ko'rinmas, chin ma'nosi bilan qorong'I kuzning qorong'I bir tuni edi. Bir necha yuz yillardan beri yashab favqulodda zo'rayib ketgan "Xo'ja Maoz" mozorining chakaligi bu qorong'iliq qabir manba' kabi edi. Kuchlik bir yel turg'an, qandaydir bir ishga hozirlang'an kabi to'rt tomong'a yugurib yuraredi. Mozor chakaligining bir burchagida tutab yotg'an to'nka yonida sochlari o'sib soqolig'a qo'shilib ketgan bir devona bu mudhish qorong'iliq qarshi kurashkan kabi gulxanni yondirishg'a tirishar, gulxan tavaragida naylanib

³Hamidov H. "Presentation of the image of nature in the translation of a work of art", Translation Issues (Collection of scientific articles, April 26, 2012) pp. 75-77.

⁴Qadiri A. "Otkankunlar", Tashkent, G'. Ghulam ed., 1992.

qo'lidag'I kasavi bilan to'rt tomonidan kavlar edi. Yel borg'an sarik uchlana bordi, chakalak tartibsiz holg'a kirib ketdi, bitta-yarimta to'kilmay qolg'an yaproqlar shitir-shitir to'kilishka oldilar, qarg'a va zog'chalar ayni uyqu zamonida tinchsizlangani uchun yelga qarshi namoyish qilg'andek g'o-g'ubila chakalak ustidan aylana boshladilar. Yel kuchaygandan kuchayib borar va shu nusbatda mozorichi ham yana bir qat qo'rqunch holg'a kirar edi, yel ketma-ket bo'kurar, bunga chidayolmag'anshox-shabbalarqars-qurssinar, keksayog'ochlar g'iyq-g'iyq etib yol boorish tovshi chiqarar edilar. Yel ortiqcha bir g'azab ustida edi, yer yuzidagi tikkaygan narsani bukib-yanchib tashlamoqchi bo'lgandek pishqirar edi..."⁵

In this passage, the translator's achievement is that "The clutter of Khoja Maoz's tomb, which had been extremely damaged after living for several hundred years, was like a source of darkness" sentence "The clutter of Khoja Maoz's tomb, which had been in existence for hundreds of years was like a source of darkness" "The thicket of Khoja Maoz's grave", which has been strained, is fully covered in the translated copy."

...the wind roared one after another, the branches that couldn't stand it were breaking, the old trees were creaking and making begging sounds..." sentence "...The wind blew one after another, and the branches that could not stand it cracked, and the old trees shrieked as they cried out in supplication..." some words are left out, for example, the branches that could not stand it cracked are completely translated as the branches that could not stand it cracked, the old woodman whimpered and in the phrase "they were making a sound" that belongs to the sentence of "old trees", the words in the phrase "they were making a sound" were omitted.

CONCLUSION

There are shortcomings in the translation of some of the scenes presented in the passage. For example, in the original text, the sentence "Although it was the fifteenth of the month, the moon was invisible with the clouds of the sky, it was literally a dark night of dark autumn" Here, the author described a dark autumn night when the moon

⁵G. Salomov, *The Art of Translation*, Tashkent, 1973, p. 57.

was covered by clouds, and in the translation it was a dark night of dark autumn. "- translated in the style of "it was a dark autumn night". At this point, the author has missed the real meaning that he wants to emphasize.

Let's continue the analysis: "The wind was overflowing with rage, squealing as if trying to crush what was standing on the earth" in English "ground" - well translated as "he was hitting the ground, blowing into the air" when he came out in front of the angry wind. We can see from this that the translator tried to express the meaning of the sentence without literal translation here and was able to do it.

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